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13-14 mai 2013, Lyon*

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ACTES DE LA TABLE RONDE

Autour de l'œuvre de Pierre Bastien.
Monnayage impérial romain – Corpus – Ateliers

13-14 mai 2013, Lyon

Rhône-Alpes ^{Région}

Maison de l'Orient et de la Méditerranée
Jean Pouilloux

CNRS - Université Lumière Lyon 2

AVANT-PROPOS

La Table Ronde «Autour de l'œuvre de Pierre Bastien. Monnayage impérial romain – Corpus – Ateliers» s'est tenue à la Maison de l'Orient et de la Méditerranée à Lyon les 13 et 14 mai 2013, c'est-à-dire pour le 3^e anniversaire de sa disparition (9 mars 1912 - 13 mai 2010).

Cette Table Ronde se veut un hommage à l'un de ceux qui portèrent le plus haut l'esprit d'une certaine «École de numismatique française», et ce sur plusieurs décennies, car Pierre Bastien publia sur quarante ans d'activité, de 1955 à 1996, une œuvre centrée sur la numismatique romaine d'époque impériale, et plus particulièrement axée sur l'Antiquité tardive, riche de 182 ouvrages et articles et de 35 comptes-rendus. Nombreux de ses travaux sont, et restent, des monuments, sommes considérables de matériel rassemblé et de science numismatique. Inlassable collecte d'un globe-trotter de la monnaie et patience méticuleuse de l'homme de cabinet : activité et production scientifiques stupéfiantes quand on songe que cette passion n'était que l'un des à-côtés d'une carrière de chirurgien bien remplie. Pierre Bastien sut y mettre les meilleures qualités du médecin, goût de l'observation, sûreté de l'œil, pragmatisme plutôt que théorisation, modestie devant les infinies variétés et combinatoires du vivant, de l'humain pour le chirurgien, de ses artefacts pour le numismate.

Bien sûr, la tenue de la Table Ronde «Autour de l'œuvre de Pierre Bastien» à Lyon n'est en rien un hasard, puisque le principal opus de Pierre Bastien est la monumentale série qu'il a consacrée au *Monnayage de l'atelier de Lyon*. Le corpus de la production monétaire de Lyon – notre «atelier romain national» – a fait l'objet d'une publication en huit volumes, parus dans la collection qu'il avait lui-même créée, *Numismatique Romaine*. Six volumes sont de sa main ; Jean-Baptiste Giard est l'auteur des deux autres ; deux Suppléments s'y sont ajoutés. La série couvre le fonctionnement d'un atelier monétaire essentiel qui fonctionna, d'abord comme monnaie coloniale à la création en 43 av. J.-C. par L. Munatius Plancus de la colonie *Copia Felix Munatia*, destinée à rester dans l'histoire sous son nom celtique de *Lugdunum* ; comme principal atelier de l'Empire pour la frappe de l'or et de l'argent sous Auguste, de 15 av. J.-C. jusqu'à la réforme de Néron en 64 apr. J.-C. lorsque la frappe des métaux précieux fut transférée à Rome ; comme atelier de circonstance au moment de l'usurpation de Clodius Albinus avant qu'il ne fût défait par Septime Sévère en 197 aux portes de Lyon dans la plaine de la Saône ; comme atelier créé par Aurélien en 274 après la défaite de l'empire gaulois et la récupération des provinces occidentales ; puis presque sans interruption comme l'un des ateliers principaux de l'Occident romain, aux côtés de Trèves et d'Arles, et jusqu'à la mort de Jovin en 413 apr. J.-C.

Le temps a depuis longtemps exercé ses ravages dans les rangs de la génération de savants numismates à laquelle appartenait Pierre Bastien. Ceux qui lui ont rendu hommage lors de cette Table Ronde et qui ont inscrit leurs travaux sous

son souvenir appartiennent aux générations suivantes, mais tous ont répondu avec enthousiasme à notre invitation tant l'œuvre de Pierre Bastien et ses méthodes paraissent un modèle à ceux qui s'intéressent à la monnaie romaine impériale et à l'établissement de corpus. Ce n'est pas un hasard si la plupart de ceux qui œuvrent actuellement à la révision du corpus de référence, le *Roman Imperial Coinage*, ont participé à cette Table Ronde.

L'hommage rendu à l'œuvre de Pierre Bastien s'est articulé autour des points forts de son travail : la représentation impériale et l'iconographie monétaire ; les trésors monétaires et les *donativa* ; les corpus, qu'ils soient corpus de règne ou corpus d'atelier. La méthode aussi s'est voulue inspirée de celle de Pierre Bastien. S'il est une des leçons premières qu'enseigne son travail, c'est celle-ci, la priorité absolue donnée aux monnaies elles-mêmes et, avant toute tentation théorique, à la collecte d'un matériel le plus exhaustif possible. S'il est facile de faire passer par deux points, deux monnaies, la ligne droite épurée d'une théorie, le long et patient rassemblement du matériel nous apprend qu'en matière de numismatique, nous voyageons au travers de nuages de points, des nébuleuses plus ou moins rebelles à la systématisation. Mais il est un moment où l'ajout d'une variante ou d'un inédit n'apporte plus rien et où la recherche de l'impossible exhaustivité stérilise la synthèse : la monnaie, tout comme le texte, l'inscription, le papyrus ou la fouille, apporte une vision partielle d'un monde disparu, mais celui qui l'édite a toute légitimité pour en faire de l'Histoire.

Il nous est particulièrement agréable de remercier ici ceux qui ont rendu possible la tenue de cette Table Ronde aujourd'hui à Lyon, ville hautement symbolique pour l'œuvre numismatique de Pierre Bastien : les institutions qui l'ont accueillie, la MOM et l'UMR HiSoMA ; les institutions qui l'ont soutenue financièrement : la Région Rhône-Alpes, l'Université Lumière Lyon-2, la Ville de Lyon, la Société française de numismatique, ainsi que la famille de Pierre Bastien. Françoise Bastien, Dominique Bastien et son épouse nous ont fait de surcroît l'amitié de traverser l'Atlantique pour y assister, qu'ils en soient vivement remerciés.

La publication des Actes de cette Table-Ronde dans la *Revue Numismatique* bénéficie du soutien financier de la famille de P. Bastien et de l'Université Lyon-3.

Le comité d'organisation,
Sylviane ESTIOT, Vincent DROST, Julie DALAISON.

Bernhard E. WOYTEK*

Heads and Busts on Roman Coins

Some Remarks on the Morphology of Numismatic Portraiture

Summary – Portraits were the standard obverse types of Roman imperial coins. Up to the mid-1st century AD, gender-specific morphological differences in the numismatic portraiture of emperors and their family members are in evidence. There were invariably portrait heads for the rulers, but draped portrait busts for imperial ladies. In this paper, the differences are analysed in detail and possible explanations are discussed. The imperial bust types are set in the context not only of Hellenistic royal coinages, but also of the heads and busts of gods and mortals appearing on Roman Republican coins – a tradition hitherto underexplored in scholarship.

Keywords – Bust, portraiture, Roman coinage, emperors, ancestors, *imagines*.

Résumé – Les portraits constituent le type de représentation habituel au droit des monnaies impériales romaines. Jusqu’au milieu du 1^{er} s. apr. J.-C., des spécificités morphologiques s’observent dans le traitement des portraits des empereurs et des membres de leurs familles. Les bustes des empereurs sont invariablement nus tandis que ceux des femmes de la *domus* impériale sont drapés. Dans cet article, ces nuances sont analysées dans le détail et les interprétations possibles sont discutées. Les différents types de bustes impériaux sont mis en regard avec les monnayages des rois hellénistiques, mais aussi avec les têtes et bustes de dieux et de mortels qui se retrouvent sur les monnaies de la République romaine – une tradition jusqu’alors sous-exploitée par les chercheurs.

Mots clés – Buste, portraits, monnayage romain, empereurs, ancêtres, *imagines*.

Roman coins have survived into the modern era in incredibly large numbers¹. Due to their wide geographical distribution as well as their portability, coins have always been the most easily accessible class of sources for the history of ancient Rome. Consequently, the role of coinage has been fundamental in shaping the modern perception of Roman culture. The salient typological element of imperial coins doubtless is the effigy of the emperor or a member of his family, which almost invariably adorns the obverse.

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1. I would like to thank Sylviane Estiot and her team for the invitation to participate in the round table “Autour de l’œuvre de Pierre Bastien” as well as for their hospitality in Lyon during the conference. Furthermore, I am grateful to Sam Moorhead for reading and commenting on a previous version of this article.

Hence it is not surprising that, of the different kinds of images on Roman issues, the imperial portraits seem to have made the biggest visual impact by far already on contemporaries.² Incidentally, the same is true for antiquaries of the early modern period. In the first half of the 16th century, numismatic literature was dominated by publications belonging to a genre commonly referred to as “Bildnisvitenbücher”.³ In these books, the portraits of famous men and women of the past were published, together with short biographical notes. The portraits are in profile and in medallic form and were mostly drawn from coins, whether genuine pieces or Renaissance forgeries. Books of this type, which were invariably centered on a series of portraits of the Roman emperors, can hardly count as scholarly publications, but they were extremely popular. Thus, Roman imperial effigies on coins were already a focus of interest in the formative phase of numismatic research. Renaissance scholars were of course aware of the fact that Roman coinage provides us with the only portrait gallery of emperors and their families in which every single image is accurately identified by a legend: it is precisely this point that has made Roman imperial coinage invaluable to Roman historians and art historians ever since.

However, another major factor is that Roman emperors were portrayed on coins in innumerable different guises. From the second half of the 1st century AD onwards, rulers are depicted wearing various forms of headgear and garments, and they carry diverse attributes. The perspectives in which they are shown vary greatly, as does the section of the imperial image the die-cutters chose to picture: sometimes heads, sometimes busts and occasionally even superb half-length figures. These bust varieties are significant manifestations of Roman imperial ideology and (self-)representation. To give an obvious example, silver multiples of Constantine the Great struck in AD 315 show an extravagant bust of the emperor facing three quarters left, with a sceptre and a shield, flanked by a horse’s head. His helmet is adorned with a christogram: hence, this issue has rightly been called the most important non-literary testimony of Constantine’s conversion to Christianity.⁴

Despite the evident importance of the bust varieties on Roman imperial coinage, numismatists for a long time largely disregarded the subject – perhaps not at least due to the sheer quantity of material awaiting systematic study. There was no treatment of the numismatic evidence for imperial effigies in its entirety until as late as the 1990s,⁵ when Pierre Bastien (1912-2010) published his seminal

2. On this point, see CRAWFORD 1983, p. 54-56, WOLTERS 1999, p. 309-311 and WOYTEK (in press). Suffice it to cite here the question asked by Jesus (*NT*, Matthew 22:20): *cuius est imago haec et suprascriptio?*

3. On them, see CUNNALLY 1999, chapter 9, p. 95-104, as well as PELC 2002, esp. p. 69ff.

4. *RIC* VII, Ticinum 36; KRAFT 1954-1955; GÖBL 1987; EHLING 2011 (for the quote: p. 27); EHLING 2012, p. 64-67.

5. There were just short overviews like BERNHART 1926, vol. 1, p. 31-37 or R.-ALFÖLDI 1978, p. 161-163 (partly unreliable), and a few specialized studies, e.g. DELBRUECK 1940 for the 3rd century.

study *Le buste monétaire des empereurs romains* in three volumes,⁶ rightly hailed as “an undertaking of breathtaking scale” by a critic.⁷ Bastien had been working on the subject for more than ten years and had produced several preliminary studies from 1980 onwards.⁸ It is not a coincidence that a numismatist specializing in 3rd and 4th century AD Roman coinage was to produce the first comprehensive work on the topic: especially in the 3rd century, both the range of bust types simultaneously in use and also the complexity of single types reached new dimensions.⁹

In his monographic study, Bastien chose to approach his subject not chronologically, but thematically. In vol. 1, he treats the various forms of headgear, garments and basic bust types of Roman emperors occurring on coins, whereas in vol. 2 he covers “Les attributs du buste et la main levée”, female and multiple busts as well as various symbols associated with imperial effigies on Roman coins. This thematic structure doubtless has its merits, but also one significant disadvantage: it obstructs the view on the chronological development of the bust types over the centuries.¹⁰ In particular, no attempt seems to have been made so far to embed the phenomenon of bust types on Roman imperial coins into the century-long tradition of depicting heads and busts on Roman coins in general: Pierre Bastien started his analysis only with the coins of 27 BC.¹¹ Furthermore, significant differences in the typological behaviour of male and female portraits in the Late Republican and the Julio-Claudian periods still await explanation.

But before we tackle these problems, some general comments about the relationship between the numismatic material and other classes of visual sources for the imperial image are needed. In his volume of plates, Bastien helpfully illustrated many comparanda from various media, particularly from gemstones, three-dimensional marble busts, statues and from state reliefs. Especially for the early Principate, it is apparent that in different media often different approaches to depicting the emperor were chosen. Perhaps the best example is provided by

6. BASTIEN 1992-1994.

7. WATSON 1995, p. 391. Among the many other reviews of the work, mainly very positive in tone, the following may be singled out: BLAND 1995, LEVY 1996, VON KAENEL 1998 (who was, however, highly critical), WEILLER 1998 and EVERS 2000.

8. See the articles BASTIEN 1980, 1981a (esp. p. 131 and 137), 1981b, 1982, 1983 and BASTIEN, ARNOLD BIUCCHI 1983.

9. An early forerunner is Trajan, for whom 36 bust types have been counted (headgear varieties notwithstanding): WOYTEK 2010, vol. 2, p. 590. The question why such a great number of different bust types was used will not be examined here. A statement by Crawford comes to mind: “the pattern for the most part is surely one of a mint doing its best for its patron” (CRAWFORD 1983, p. 59).

10. On this point, cp. already VON KAENEL 1998, p. 716f. It is true that Bastien organized the plates in vol. 3 of his work chronologically, emperor-by-emperor, but this does not compensate for a chronological narrative.

11. BASTIEN 1992-1994, vol. 1, p. 11.

the case of Augustus. The sardonyx cameo at the centre of the Cross of Lothair in Aachen cathedral treasure¹² shows the emperor in profile to the left, wearing a cuirass and *paludamentum* and holding what should be an eagle-tipped sceptre in his right hand. While this piece may confidently be dated to the reign of Augustus,¹³ the dating of two other precious stones with his portrait is disputed, viz. the Strozzi-Blacas Cameo in the British Museum and the Marlborough Cameo in the Metropolitan Museum of Art (New York).¹⁴ On them, the emperor is shown from behind, facing left, with the aegis on his left shoulder, otherwise nude, holding a spear. This representation clearly goes back to a Hellenistic prototype, as has recently been demonstrated by Renate Thomas, who suggested that it may have been modelled on an image of Alexander the Great created by the gem-engraver Pyrgoteles.¹⁵ Although the cameos depicting Augustus had both been attributed to Dioscurides by Adolf Furtwängler,¹⁶ the hypothesis of a posthumous creation in the reigns of Tiberius and Claudius respectively is preferred today.¹⁷ For us, this does not make much of a difference: on Roman imperial coins, Augustus was never pictured with an aegis – neither during his lifetime nor posthumously –, and he never appears in cuirass and *paludamentum* holding an eagle-tipped sceptre either. He is depicted with several different headgears (as well as bareheaded),¹⁸ but his portrait on coins is nearly always truncated at the neck and undraped.¹⁹ This means that in the Julio-Claudian period to some extent different artistic conventions for depicting the emperor are to be observed in different media.

But we can go even one step further. Sometimes, there were different artistic conventions in different numismatic media, too. A good example is the bust of a prince on the obverse of an imperial bronze *tessera* of the Julio-Claudian period (figure 1). The type is part of a group of *tesserae* with various imperial

12. ZWIERLEIN-DIEHL 2007, plate 127, no. 608; VOLLENWEIDER 1966, plate 74, no. 2.

13. ZWIERLEIN-DIEHL 2007, p. 148 (whose interpretation of the sceptre as *aquila* en miniature I cannot follow).

14. ZWIERLEIN-DIEHL 2007, plate 131, nos. 621-622; VOLLENWEIDER 1966, plate 60, no. 1 and plate 72, no. 3.

15. THOMAS 1995, p. 378f. See also KÜHNEN 2008, p. 28-30 on this problem.

16. FURTWÄNGLER 1900, vol. 3, p. 316f.

17. ZWIERLEIN-DIEHL 2007, p. 158.

18. Laurel wreath and oak wreath occur on lifetime issues, the radiate crown on posthumous coins: cp. SUTHERLAND 1984, plate 4, no. 198 *etc.* (laurel wreath), plate 6, no. 298 (oak wreath) and plate 12, nos. 74, 77 and 79 (*corona radiata*).

19. Two exceptions were illustrated by BASTIEN 1992-1994, vol. 3, plate 2, nos. 2-3. One obverse die used for the famous “heifer” aurei of Augustus (*RIC* I², 536-538; BAHRFELDT 1923, nos. 137-139), probably struck in the East in the 20s BC, shows a laureate effigy of Augustus to the left with a somewhat deeper bust (RAMBACH, WALKER 2012, p. 41f., obverse die no. 6). Furthermore, on some of the “triumphal asses” struck in 7 BC at the mint of Rome, the bust of Augustus terminates in a globe (SUTHERLAND 1984, p. 75, bust D; on the date of the series, see already WILLERS 1909, p. 175f.).

effigies (Augustus, Divus Augustus, Tiberius, Livia *etc.*) and other images on the obverse and Roman numerals on the reverse. This series, which is intimately die-linked to the so-called *spintriae*,²⁰ has been dated to the reign of Tiberius, c. AD 22-37, by T.V. Buttrey.²¹ The prince depicted on our *tessera* was identified as “Germanicus?” by Buttrey and Göbl,²² and they may well be right.²³ He is bareheaded and shown in profile to the right; the bust, seen from behind, is most unusual: the prince wears a cuirass decorated with a star of four rays at the back. The *pteryges* on both shoulders are visible, and a sword belt (*balteus*) is in evidence across his back. Behind the head, there is a rod-shaped transverse object, in all probability a spear. It should be emphasized that on imperial coins and medallions, comparable cuirassed busts seen from the back do not appear before the joint rule of Marcus Aurelius and Lucius Verus;²⁴ the spear occurs on medallions from Marcus Aurelius onwards, but is used on the regular imperial coinage not earlier than the 3rd century AD.²⁵ Hence, the obverse of this *tessera* is running ahead of the iconography of imperial coins and medallions by about one and a half centuries, if Buttrey’s dating is correct.²⁶ Although the majority of the portrait *tesserae* of the group feature images more in line with ordinary numismatic practice of the period, the case of the armoured bust is very instructive: on non-monetary numismatic objects – “*Pseudomoneta*” in Eckhel’s classic terminology²⁷ – the boundaries of iconographic conventions of the genre could be pushed. For our purpose, this means that we should focus on the evidence provided by coinage in the following analysis.

The officials responsible for the design of Roman imperial busts on coins could theoretically draw on two main groups of numismatic reference material: Hellenistic coins on the one hand and earlier Roman (Republican) issues on the other. We will just briefly touch upon the Hellenistic royal coinages here. As far as ruler portraits are concerned, these series provided an ample array of typologically different prototypes. In some series, for example on Macedonian issues of the second century BC or on Seleukid silver, kings’ heads (cut off at

20. BUTTREY 1973, p. 56f.; GÖBL 1978, vol. 2, p. 129f. and plate 8.

21. BUTTREY 1973, p. 55.

22. BUTTREY 1973, p. 62; GÖBL 1978, vol. 2, p. 130.

23. DE BELFORT 1889, p. 86f. had unconvincingly proposed to identify the man as “Tibère?”.

See also n. 26 below.

24. BASTIEN 1992-1994, vol. 1, p. 267f. (here the emperor wears the *lorica squamata*).

25. BASTIEN 1992-1994, vol. 2, p. 437.

26. The singularity of the bust type of course makes the question of the identity of the man depicted even more pressing. In this context, it should be remembered that Germanicus was likened to Alexander the Great by the Romans (Tac. *ann.* 2.73.1-3; cp. LEHMANN 1971 and esp. KÜHNEN 2008, p. 141-146), although the bust type used on the *tessera* does not seem to have obvious parallels to Alexander’s imagery on coins as compiled by DAHMEN 2007.

27. ECKHEL 1798, p. 277.

the neck) prevailed,²⁸ while other dynasties provided models of portraits with deep, richly draped busts, occasionally featuring additional attributes like a spear. Apart from the artistically brilliant Greco-Bactrian and Indo-Greek series, which – for obvious reasons – will hardly have provided direct inspiration for Roman coin designs, special mention must be made of the Ptolemaic coins in this context. Since the reign of the dynasty's founder Ptolemy I Soter (305/4-283/2 BC), who was depicted on his coins wearing the aegis,²⁹ some tradition developed for Ptolemaic monarchs to be represented in extraordinary guises especially on precious metal coinage. A well-known case is the portrait of Ptolemy III (246-222 BC) with the rays of Helios, the aegis of Zeus and Poseidon's trident – the middle prong of which terminates in a lotus finial – on gold octodrachms (figure 2) minted by his son Ptolemy IV (222-205 BC). On coins of the same denomination, Ptolemy V (205-180 BC) is depicted with rays, wearing a chlamys and carrying a spear over his shoulder (figure 3). It seems likely that the radiate crown of the (deified) Roman emperors was essentially inspired by the "aureole" of Ptolemaic rulers.³⁰ The same may be true of the aegis, occurring on Roman imperial numismatic effigies from Nero onward.³¹ In some cases, the immediate influence of Ptolemaic prototypes on Roman numismatic bust types is unmistakable. For instance, the deep bust depicting Ptolemy III wearing the aegis was clearly the model for the obverse of medallic sestertii of Trajan (98-117; figure 4).³²

But the main source of inspiration for Roman die cutters of the imperial period was probably the numismatic repertoire of forms of the Republic. The depiction of heads and busts on Roman coins goes back to the beginning of the 3rd century BC, when, following the Greek custom, gods and goddesses adorned the obverses of Roman issues. At the beginning, in the phase of Rome's didrachm coinage, there was the tendency to truncate effigies at the neck; the first obverse to exhibit some "drapery" and an attribute was the image of Hercules with his lion-skin tied around the neck and a club at the shoulder (*RRC* 20/1). Towards the end of the 3rd century, draped busts (showing also part of the upper body) began to appear (see, e. g., *RRC* 39/5 in figure 5); from this point in time

28. For a concise typological overview, see MØRKHOLM 1991, plates 39 and 42f. In the Seleukid series, effigies of kings draped with the chlamys occur, too, but there are no deep busts.

29. MØRKHOLM 1991, p. 65. This was the earliest individual portrait of a Hellenistic ruler; it was repeated on the silver coins of his successors Ptolemy II and Ptolemy III and also later.

30. On this attribute in general, see the monograph by BERGMANN 1998; on terminology – she carefully distinguishes the "Strahlenaureole" of Hellenistic rulers from the Roman "Strahlenkrone" (*corona radiata*) – cp. BERGMANN p. 13-15. Of course both attributes refer to the rays of Helios/Sol. A detailed discussion of the aureole in Ptolemaic and Seleukid coinage (where it derives from the Ptolemaic model) is provided by BERGMANN 1998, p. 58-66.

31. BASTIEN 1992-1994, vol. 2, p. 345 and 350ff.

32. WOYTEK 2010, p. 87 and no. 338u. This bust type was later used for medallions from Hadrian onward, see MITTAG 2010, Hadrian nos. 126-128, and BASTIEN 1992-1994, vol. 2, p. 346.

onwards, divine heads and busts were used side by side on Roman Republican issues. For example, in the standard obverse type of the early denarius the helmeted head of Roma is usually truncated immediately below the goddess's necklace. By way of contrast, on the first denarius type departing from this denomination's traditional iconography, struck in the 130s BC (*RRC* 234/1: figure 6), a helmeted bust of Mars forms the obverse type. It is draped, with a round *fibula* holding the cloak together on the right shoulder. Deep busts are frequently encountered in Roman Republican numismatic depictions of Minerva (wearing the aegis) or the winged goddess Victory.³³

A group of obverse types of Roman Republican coins which is particularly momentous for our subject shall be singled out. I would like to draw attention to the existence of a cluster of what seem to be experimental obverses of a high artistic quality in the period c. 113-111 BC, on Crawford's chronology. The denarii of P. Licinius Nerva (*RRC* 292/1, figure 7) are well-known for the voting scene depicted on their reverse, but the helmeted bust of Roma to the left with spear and shield on the obverse is equally remarkable.³⁴ Perhaps in the following year, extravagant busts of Hercules and a youthful god holding a thunderbolt in his right hand appeared on denarii signed by TI. Q and L. CAESI. Both busts face left and are seen from behind (*RRC* 297/1 and 298/1: figures 8-9). The unusual bust of Hercules was repeated on a quadrans of the same year.³⁵

These extraordinary creations clearly made an impact on Roman coin design in the decades to follow. A deep bust of Hercules shouldering his club, seen from behind, reappeared around 100 BC, this time facing right (*RRC* 329/1: figure 10), and the youthful, thunderbolt-hurling god was faithfully copied on denarii of C. Licinius Macer around 84 BC (*RRC* 354/1: figure 11). But there were also new designs, based on the same iconographic concept. Especially in view of later developments in the imperial period already briefly mentioned above, the bust of Mars on the obverse of the denarii signed by the *monetalis* Cn. Lentulus is instructive (*RRC* 345/1: figure 12). The god, with long hair, wears a crested helmet and is seen from behind, facing right. There is a sword belt across his naked upper body and a spear over his left shoulder. This image may be compared with the obverse of the rare denarii of M. Valerius Messalla, struck in 53 BC (*RRC* 435/1: figure 13). His coins are much-quoted because of their reverse legend PATRE COS, indicating that the moneyer held office during his father's consulship. Their obverses show, again, a helmeted bust with long hair to the right, seen from behind, with a spear over the left shoulder. Since there is no sword belt, but just (on some dies) a touch of drapery at the back, the

33. Cp. *RRC* 328/1, 465/5 and 494/38 (Minerva) and *RRC* 365/1, 464/4f. and 475/1 (Victory). For a useful typological overview of Republican coin types, see ALTERI 1990.

34. This obverse type was revived with some modifications on aurei of 42 BC: cp. *RRC* 494/35; it also occurs on a gem: FURTWÄNGLER 1900, vol. 3, plate 25, no. 34 (with the description in vol. 2, p. 127).

35. *RRC* 296/4 (Cn. Blasio Cn. f.). All of these obverse types were sadly left out by BÖHM 1997.

deity is commonly identified not as Mars, but as Roma.³⁶ Finally, a discussion of busts of this type on Roman Republican coins would not be complete without a mention of the enigmatic denarii of Q. Crepereius M. f. Rocus, struck in the late 70s or early 60s BC (*RRC* 399/1³⁷: figure 14). On their reverse, Neptune is depicted in a biga of sea-horses, whereas the god's consort Amphitrite occupies the obverse: her bust is richly draped and is – most unusually for a female effigy – seen from behind, with her hair falling down her neck.

All in all, it is evident that many busts of gods, heroes and goddesses on Roman Republican coins contained iconographic elements which were later re-used on Roman imperial bust types. Some of these Republican images may even be regarded as direct antecedents of imperial obverse types. Busts with a cloak and a *fibula* like the bust of Mars in figure 6 very much resemble draped busts of the High Principate.³⁸ The helmeted bust of Roma with spear and shield to the left is closely akin to numismatic busts of 3rd century emperors³⁹ (figure 7). More generally, images such as this bust of Roma (or the busts of Hercules with his club, figures 8 and 10) foreshadowed the practice to depict emperors' busts with various attributes.⁴⁰ Furthermore, the fashion to display Roman imperial busts in a perspective from behind, in evidence especially on coins from the 2nd century AD onward, goes back to the Republican precedents discussed in detail above.

But it would be completely mistaken to try to distinguish neatly between Roman imperial bust types going back to Roman Republican models and others borrowed from Hellenistic coinages. This would create a false dichotomy, since the alternatives overlap. In designing their coin images, the Republican artists were clearly borrowing elements from a common pool of Hellenistic heroic or religious imagery, as can also be exemplified nicely by the deep busts seen from behind, discussed above. Especially the images of the youthful god hurling a thunderbolt in figures 9 and 11 – earlier believed to represent Veiovis, but identified as Apollo by Crawford⁴¹ – invite a comparison with various similar representations in Hellenistic art.⁴² On coins, perhaps the most impressive

36. See CRAWFORD 1974, p. 457; HOLLSTEIN 1993, p. 356.

37. On this coin type, see also HOLLSTEIN 1993, p. 99-103.

38. E.g. WOYTEK 2010, p. 87f.: Trajan's bust type "v".

39. BASTIEN 1992-1994, vol. 3, plate 119, no. 4, and plate 120, no. 3 (Probus); plate 127, no. 4 (Carus) *etc.*

40. Of course, many more examples of busts of gods with attributes over their shoulder could be cited from the Republican coinage: cp., e.g., Vulcan with tongs (*RRC* 314/1), Mercury with his *caduceus* (*RRC* 362/1), Apollo with bow and quiver on a rare variety of *RRC* 408/1b (for an image, see Numismatik Lanz, München, 123, 30 May 2005, lot 331) or Mars with a trophy (*RRC* 429/1).

41. *RRC* p. 312; GRUEBER 1910, vol. 1, p. 320 and vol. 2, p. 290. Erika Simon, who had earlier identified the god as Veiovis, too, later followed Crawford: SIMON 1990, p. 31.

42. See the catalogue by THOMAS 1995, p. 392ff., especially p. 402ff.

parallel is provided by obverses displaying the heroic helmeted bust of the Greco-Bactrian king Eukratides (c. 170-145 BC) seen from behind, hurling a spear (figure 15).⁴³

On Roman Republican coins, there are but few portraits of foreigners in general and of Hellenistic rulers in particular. The most famous one is the portrait of Philip V on the denarii of L. Marcius Philippus (*RRC* 293/1) – a helmeted head, truncated at the neck (figure 16). The diademed bust clad in a lion-skin on the obverse of a denarius type of Faustus Sulla (*RRC* 426/2) was convincingly interpreted as the portrait of king Bocchus of Mauretania by Wilhelm Hollstein.⁴⁴ The Gaul depicted on the famous denarii of Caesar's moneyer L. Hostilius Saserna (*RRC* 448/2) can of course not be demonstrated to be Vercingetorix, as earlier scholarship often posited.⁴⁵ His bust is shown with a peculiar attire which has not been explained satisfactorily up to now – presumably a characteristic Gallic outfit (figure 17).⁴⁶ The denarii of king Juba I of Numidia (60-46 BC) are roughly contemporary with these coins; they were produced at the very end of Juba's reign, during the *Bellum Africum*.⁴⁷ Although they are technically the product of a Roman client kingdom, it seems justified to treat them in the present context: their Latin obverse legend REX IVBA, the style of engraving and the use of the Roman denominational system all point to heavy Roman involvement in the production of this issue, which also comprised quinarii and sestertii. The denarius obverse shows the king's deep bust to the right, seen from the front, wearing a cuirass (with *pteryges* in evidence) and a cloak, with a long sceptre over his right shoulder. To sum up, on Roman Republican (and closely associated) denarius issues, the few portraits of non-Romans could either take the form of heads or of busts. This is in parallel with the depictions of gods, heroes and goddesses on the obverses of Roman Republican coins, for which heads and busts occur side by side: as pointed out above, there is no clear pattern.

This is in complete contrast with the portraits of Roman males on Roman coins of the Late Republic and the early Julio-Claudian period. It does not seem to have been hitherto appreciated adequately that these portraits are never draped, but that they all take the form of head portraits, truncated at the neck. Obviously, it is not possible to illustrate and discuss all of them in the present context: these images are too numerous.⁴⁸ But we will sketch out the development of Roman portraiture on coins and present its salient points.

43. BOPEARACHCHI 1991, Eucratide I, série 8 (plate 19). But see also the gemstone probably depicting Philip V, wearing the aegis and hurling a spear: THOMAS 1995, p. 371f., no. 11 (= FURTWÄNGLER 1900, vol. 3, p. 159, no. 113, who opted for an identification as Perseus).

44. HOLLSTEIN 1991, p. 281-283.

45. Cp. GRUEBER 1910, vol. 1, p. 513.

46. This is sometimes misinterpreted as a chain round his neck: TOYNBEE 1978, p. 102.

47. *RPC* I, 717; WOYTEK 2003, p. 240-245 (with further bibliography).

48. For listings, compare CRAWFORD 1974, p. 746-748, and LAHUSEN 1989, p. 35. The latter monograph is to be used with caution, see CRAWFORD 1990.

The fashion to portray ancestors on Roman Republican denarii started only in the mid-50s BC, when the future tyrannicide M. Iunius Brutus, as a moneyer, chose to depict the bearded heads of L. Iunius Brutus (cos. 509 BC) and C. Servilius Ahala (*magister equitum* 439 BC) on one of his denarius types (*RRC* 433/2, figure 18). Perhaps in the same year, the moneyer Q. Pompeius Rufus portrayed his homonymous paternal grandfather as well as his maternal grandfather L. Cornelius Sulla on his denarius type *RRC* 434/1 (figure 19). In the later fifties and early forties BC, several *monetales* opted for expressive portrait heads of famous family members as coin types.⁴⁹ Prominent examples of portrait subjects are C. Coelius Caldus, who was the moneyer's grandfather (*RRC* 437), Cn. Cornelius Lentulus Marcellinus, the moneyer's father (*RRC* 439),⁵⁰ as well as C. Antius Restio, also the moneyer's father (*RRC* 455/1, figure 20). In the Civil War between Pompey and Caesar, the Pompeians used the effigy of Pompey the Great on a series of denarii struck in Spain, a couple of years after the leader of the anti-Caesarian coalition had been assassinated in Egypt (*RRC* 470). Invariably, these portraits do not display the folds of a toga, a military cloak or a cuirass: only the ancestors' heads are shown. As Hans Werner Ritter has demonstrated conclusively, the ancestor portraits on Roman coins of the fifties and forties BC must be understood as crucial precursors of the portraiture of Julius Caesar (100-44 BC) on the quattuorviral denarii of the dictator's year of death (*RRC* 480).⁵¹

It is well known that Caesar was the first Roman to be honoured by the senate with the numismatic *ius imaginis* during his lifetime. In the same senatorial decree Caesar received the honorific "Father of the Fatherland" (*parens patriae*)⁵² which occasionally appears on coins, too.⁵³ Caesar's head was depicted on silver issues of 44 BC with a wreath (figure 21); sometimes he was shown *capite velato*.⁵⁴ After Caesar's assassination on the Ides of March denarii with Mark Antony's veiled portrait were struck (figure 22)⁵⁵ – he had been Caesar's colleague in the consulship 44 BC. From then on, portrait heads of political leaders became a staple feature of Roman coinage. Already in the Civil Wars after Caesar's death almost all the *imperatores* contending for power (except for C. Cassius) had their likenesses placed on their issues, and there is an absolute continuity from these imperial coinages to the issues of Augustus and his successors.

49. On these coin portraits in general see ZEHACKER 1961 and ZEHACKER 1973, vol. 2, p. 994-1007 ("La première école du réalisme romain").

50. The correct identification of this bust was first suggested by LAHUSEN 1989, p. 20f.

51. RITTER 1988. On Caesar's portrait on the coins of 44 BC, see more recently also SUSPÈNE 2008 and 2012.

52. See Cass. Dio 44.4.4: πρὸς τε τούτοις τοιοῦτοις οὐσι πατέρα τε αὐτὸν τῆς πατρίδος ἐπωνόμασαν καὶ ἐς τὰ νομίσματα ἐνεχάραξαν.

53. *RRC* 480/19f.

54. *RRC* 480/2-20. The types with veiled heads are 480/12-16 and 19f.

55. *RRC* 480/22.

The few coin portraits of Julius Caesar and Mark Antony with a veil remained completely isolated. Up to the reign of Claudius (AD 41-54), portraits of the emperors on the imperial “mainstream” coinage consistently showed just their heads (bare or with some headgear), cut off at the neck,⁵⁶ without even a touch of drapery (figure 23).⁵⁷ It is only with the issues featuring Nero Caesar that draped busts of male Romans begin to appear on imperial coin types.⁵⁸ Hence, the practice to display just the portrait heads of Romans – whether it be ancestors, political and military leaders or emperors – is to be observed for more than a century on Roman “mainstream” coinage.

This iconographic continuity in coin images of Roman males is all the more remarkable since women’s coin portraits of the same period regularly show draped busts. This difference is conspicuous already on the first coin type in precious metal featuring the representation of a Roman lady,⁵⁹ viz. Antony’s unique aureus from the Castagneto hoard, now in Berlin, struck in 39 BC (figures 24 and 24a).⁶⁰ While Antony’s head on the obverse is cut off at the neck, there is a slight drapery at the bust of his wife Octavia, pictured on the reverse.⁶¹ The importance of this coin seems to be considerable. Recently, it has been called the “first safely dated evidence for the existence of the freestanding bust” in Roman art.⁶² The next numismatic representation of Octavia on precious metal coins is the exception that proves the rule, since it is truncated like a male portrait.⁶³ From then on, the disparity between male and female busts on coins remained constant for several decades. On the denarii and the tetradrachms depicting Antony on one and Cleopatra on the other side,⁶⁴ the imbalance between the male head and the female bust is particularly obvious (see figures 25-26); in Cleopatra’s case, the Ptolemaic tradition of deep busts on coins will certainly have played its part. As far as provincial coinages of the triumviral period are concerned, Mark Antony’s cistophori and the various series of his “fleet coinage” in bronze provide important material because of the jugate and facing heads/busts on the obverses. On the cistophori depicting the jugate effigies of Antony and his wife Octavia (figure 27)⁶⁵ usually her draped bust (in the background) is

56. Typically, on early imperial coins the truncation is a little curved, indicating the neck muscles.

57. On provincial issues, this was not always the case, to be sure. See, for example, *RPC I*, 963-965, Cretan silver coins struck under Caligula (AD 37-41), with a slight drapery at the emperor’s neck and a sceptre at his shoulder.

58. *RIC I*, Claudius 75ff.

59. I deliberately omit here the quinarii *RRC* 489/5-6 with a bust of Victoria with Fulvia’s features on the obverse: on these coins, see FISCHER 1999, p. 141-165. See also n. 67 below.

60. *RRC* 527/1; VON SALLET 1884; BAHRFELDT 1923, no. 88.

61. As already recognized by BAHRFELDT 1923, p. 83 (“am Halse scheint etwas Gewand angedeutet”).

62. FEJFER 2008, p. 237. The reference given *ibid.*, p. 481, n. 42 is mistaken (read Sydenham “no. 1196” for “no. 1200”).

63. *RRC* 533/3 (38 BC).

64. *RRC* 543/1; *RPC I*, 4094-4096.

65. *RPC I*, 2202.

coupled with Antony's head. Similarly, the fleet bronzes, struck in three different mints of the Eastern Mediterranean, invariably feature Octavia's draped bust in combination with the heads of Antony and Octavian.⁶⁶

Draped female busts were used alongside male heads on imperial as well as provincial coinages in the early Principate, too. Leaving out supposed images of female members of the imperial family in mythological and other guises,⁶⁷ one may cite the busts of Agrippina the Elder on coins of her son Caligula (AD 37-41; see figure 23)⁶⁸ as well as numerous busts of Agrippina the Elder, her daughter Agrippina the Younger and Antonia (figure 28) on the issues of Claudius (AD 41-54).⁶⁹ Again, jugate effigies provide nice evidence for the gender specific iconographic differentiation in Rome: the bust of Agrippina the Younger is juxtaposed with the head of the emperor Claudius on cistophori (figure 29).⁷⁰ Change is heralded only by the conjoined busts of Nero and his mother Agrippina on aurei and denarii struck early in Nero's reign, in AD 55: here, the woman's draped bust is accompanied by her son's bust with drapery on the left shoulder.⁷¹ Under Nero's rule, a new era of Roman coin design was to begin: with the use of the radiate crown and the aegis as attributes of the living emperor, as well as with the introduction of cuirassed effigies, a Hellenization of the Roman imperial bust set in. After Nero, the next leap forward in development occurred under Trajan, when a tendency towards deeper busts of the emperor on coins is noticeable.⁷²

The above observations on the different shapes of male and female portraits on Late Republican and Julio-Claudian coins beg several questions.⁷³ The most obvious ones are whether these differences are casual or not – and if they are not,

66. *RPC* I, 1453-1470 (Atratinus, Capito) and 4088-4093 (Bibulus). Note that the catalogue entries in *RPC* do not always accurately distinguish between "heads" and "busts". On the fleet coinage see also FISCHER 1999, p. 191-211.

67. E.g. *RIC* I², Augustus 403 (Diana/"Julia"). On theomorphic representations of Roman women see also BERGMANN 1998, p. 38f.

68. *RIC* I², 7f., 13f., 21f., 30, 55.

69. *RIC* I², 65-68, 75, 80f., 92, 102-104.

70. *RPC* I, 2224, see also 2223. In this context, the early imperial *tesserae* with the jugate portraits of an imperial couple must be mentioned, probably Augustus (laureate head) and Livia (draped bust): BUTTREY 1973, p. 61, type 11; GÖBL 1978, vol. 2, plate 8, nos. 74-75. For glyptic parallels, see ZWIERLEIN-DIEHL 2007, plate 129, no. 613 – jugate effigies of Augustus (laureate head) and Livia (draped bust) – and plate 132, no. 624 – jugate effigies of Tiberius (laureate head) and Livia (draped bust).

71. *RIC* I², Nero 6f.

72. See already BERNHART 1926, vol. 1, p. 32 on this point. On the relationship of this important numismatic development with the introduction of the so-called "Dezennalientypus" in Trajan's portraiture, see WOYTEK 2010, vol. 1, p. 67-73.

73. Up to now, the fact that female portraits on Roman coins are always draped has occasionally been noted, but not contextualized. See, e.g., R.-ALFÖLDI 1978, p. 162f.: "Die Damendarstellungen zeigen immer Büsten mit fein ausgearbeiteten Kleidern". In this context an observation by DAHMEN 2001, p. 50 and 89 on Roman (non-numismatic) small-scale portraits may be cited: in this material, female busts – both imperial and private – are nearly always draped, too.

what is behind them. The fact that male and female portraits were consistently represented in a distinct manner on coins, over many decades, makes it clear that different typological conventions were in operation here. The described dissimilarities can hardly be completely fortuitous, but some “will to form” seems to be in evidence. As pointed out, female portraits appeared on Roman coins about 15 years later than male portraits. For the two sexes, different portrait forms were established: while male portraits had always been conceived as heads, female portraits were designed as busts from the start. In this development, the ornate robes of Roman ladies may have been a factor:⁷⁴ the artists may simply have deemed them worthy to be displayed. Male portraits, by contrast, clung to the Republican model until Claudius and Nero, when a morphological convergence between male and female representations on coins took place.

This leaves us with the question why in the Late Roman Republic numismatic portraits of Roman males were never draped.⁷⁵ It has already been noted that the exclusiveness with which male heads (as opposed to busts) occur on coins was a Roman tradition. Comparison with several Hellenistic coin types featuring jugate portraits of royal couples confirms this. On the famous Ptolemaic octodrachms with the jugate portraits of Ptolemy II (246-222 BC) and Arsinoe II (obverse) as well as Ptolemy I and Berenice I (reverse), the kings are draped and the queens are veiled (see figure 30). Similarly, the conjoined busts of Heliokles and Laodike, the parents of the Greco-Bactrian king Eukratides, as well as the busts of the Indo-Greek king Hermaios (c. 90-70 BC) and his wife Calliope all are draped in some way.⁷⁶ The same holds true for the busts of Kamnaskires, king of Elymais, and his queen Anzaze.⁷⁷ Artistic considerations apparently did not prevent the die engravers responsible for the design of these Hellenistic coins from depicting busts of both men and women. Hence, it is

74. On these, see ALFÖLDI 1970, p. 144-146, and BASTIEN 1992-1994, vol. 2, p. 637-642 (partly correcting Alföldi). Literary evidence on the *chlamys aurata* worn by Agrippina the Younger is provided by Tac. *ann.* 12.56.3 and Plin. *n. h.* 33.63.

75. As stated above, this paper is mainly concerned with the numismatic evidence, which is well datable. As far as the glyptic evidence is concerned, several good parallels to the undraped ancestor heads as seen on coins have been published, cp. e.g. LAHUSEN 1985, plate 115. On the other hand, there are also male draped portraits on portrait gems which have been assigned to the Late Republic, see VOLLENWEIDER 1972-1974, plates 70, 77 and 124f.; in part, Eastern influence has been claimed for these (VOLLENWEIDER 1972-1974, p. 83f.). In general, however, there are chronological and methodological issues with this class of images: “the problems of dating gems by style alone are legion and inevitably reduce much modern analysis to mere speculation” (FLOWER 1996, p. 86). Hence, it has been decided not to base the argumentation in this paper on glyptic evidences.

76. BOPEARACHCHI 1991, Eucratide I, séries 13-16; Hermaios et Calliope, séries 1-2.

77. ALRAM 1986, nos. 454-457. The tetradrachms of the Seleukid king Alexander I Balas (150-145 BC) and Cleopatra Thea are an exception in that the bust of the queen (as Tyche) is in the foreground and draped, whereas the king’s head is in the background: HOUGHTON, SPAER, LORBER 1998, no. 1483. These coins probably influenced the coinage of Cleopatra Thea and Antiochos VIII (125-121 BC), cp. *ibid.*, nos. 2437-2440 *etc.*

difficult to imagine why Roman artists responsible for coin dies should have had a priori reservations against this iconographic concept – especially since they were demonstrably familiar with male draped busts as such, for example from earlier Roman issues depicting gods.

The conjecture that the graphic solution chosen for male portraits in the Late Republican coinage might have had a cultural background of some sort seems to suggest itself. The context of the first appearance of ancestors' portraits on Roman coins, in the 50s BC, might hold the key. From the late 2nd century onward, Republican coinage had become a medium in which the mint magistrates celebrated political and military achievements of their forebears and glorified their families. This development was unique to Rome, in the ancient numismatic landscape. Apart from coins, among the most characteristic expressions of Roman gentilician pride one may cite wax masks of ancestors, the so-called *imagines maiorum* (or *cerae*), which were kept in cupboards (*armaria*) in the *atria* of the houses of the nobility.⁷⁸ These masks were central to the social identity of Rome's leading families, since it was through the number of their *imagines* that the competing clans defined their status. Only family members who had held at least the office of aedile were represented in these masks;⁷⁹ consequently, there were no female *cerae*, of course.⁸⁰ Despite occasional assertions to the contrary, there do not seem to be compelling grounds for connecting them with death masks.⁸¹ The *imagines* were realistic masks, in all probability made during the subject's lifetime; the families had the right to display them, worn by actors, during family funerals.⁸²

78. For a recent authoritative study (including an exhaustive collection of *testimonia* on p. 281-325), see FLOWER 1996; see also BADEL 2005, esp. p. 106-154. Apparently this was an ancient custom in Rome; when we first hear about the phenomenon in the 2nd century BC, it was already fully developed, see FLOWER 1996, p. 46f.

79. FLOWER 1996, p. 2 and 61. Cic. Verr. 5.36 (on the future prerogatives of a *designatus aedilis: ius imaginis ad memoriam posteritatemque prodendae*).

80. FLOWER 1996, p. 7, Badel 2005, p. 115, n. 1, and FITTSCHEN, ZANKER, CAIN 2010, p. 50 with n. 19.

81. This is the theory defended by DRERUP 1980, p. 109 and 119f. (on this point completely misunderstood by FLOWER 1996, p. 2); see also JACKSON 1987, p. 46. For arguments against this theory, see FLOWER 1996, p. 37f. and LAHUSEN 2010, p. 208 (accepted by LANG 2009, p. 386).

82. Plin. *n. h.* 35.6: *aliter apud maiores in atriis haec erant, quae spectarentur: non signa externorum artificum nec aera aut marmora; expressi cera vultus singulis disponebantur armariis, ut essent imagines, quae comitarentur gentilicia funera, semperque defuncto aliquo totus aderat familiae eius, qui umquam fuerat populus.* On the funerals, see Pol. 6.53.4-10, especially 4-7: (4) μετὰ δὲ ταῦτα θάψαντες καὶ ποιήσαντες τὰ νομιζόμενα τιθέασι τὴν εἰκόνα τοῦ μεταλλάξαντος εἰς τὸν ἐπιφανέστατον τόπον τῆς οἰκίας, ξύλινα ναΐδια περιτιθέντες. (5) ἢ δ' εἰκὼν ἐστὶ πρόσωπον εἰς ὁμοίτητα διαφερόντως ἐξεργασμένον καὶ κατὰ τὴν πλάσιν καὶ κατὰ τὴν ὑπογραφὴν. (6) ταύτας δὴ τὰς εἰκόνας ἐν τε ταῖς δημοτελέεσι θυσίαις ἀνοίγοντες κοσμοῦσι φιλοτίμως, ἐπὶ τε τῶν οἰκείων μεταλλάξει τις ἐπιφανῆς, ἄγουσιν εἰς τὴν ἐκφορὰν, περιτιθέντες ὡς ὁμοιοτάτοις εἶναι δοκοῦσι κατὰ τε τὸ μέγεθος καὶ τὴν ἄλλην περικοπήν. (7) οὗτοι δὲ προσαναλαμβάνουσι ἐσθήτας, ἐὰν μὲν ὕπατος ἢ στρατηγὸς ἢ γεγωνός,

M. Iunius Brutus was the first Roman moneyer – or at least among the first – to depict ancestors other than mythical kings on his coins (see figure 18).⁸³ Of course, L. Iunius Brutus and C. Servilius Ahala were also among the *imagines* in the home of M. Brutus, as a passing remark by Cicero in the second Philippic attests.⁸⁴ He was patently obsessed with his descent. From other literary sources we know that he had asked Atticus to provide him with an accurate family tree, including (images of) the two tyrannicides, for one of his villas.⁸⁵ His peculiar choice of coin types ties in neatly with this story. It is not unlikely that the two coin portraits go back to three-dimensional prototypes, perhaps in Brutus's possession.⁸⁶

Can the *imagines* of wax have provided inspiration for these and similar coin images? Unfortunately, no remains of such wax masks survive, nor do we possess any ancient depictions of them.⁸⁷ Our only sources on the *cerae* are textual, and they do not provide any accurate physical descriptions. Harriet I. Flower, in her standard work on the subject, was not even able to determine whether they covered the whole head or only the face.⁸⁸ Given this, it is obvious that considerations about possible iconographic influences exercised by the ancestor masks are bound to be largely hypothetical. What seems clear, however, is that they must have been akin to theatre masks in having eye holes and holes allowing

περιπορφύρους, ἐὰν δὲ τιμητῆς, πορφυράς, ἐὰν δὲ καὶ τεθριαμβευκῶς ἢ τι τοιοῦτον κατειργασμένος, διαχρῦσους. “(4) Next after the interment and the performance of the usual ceremonies, they place the image of the departed in the most conspicuous position in the house, enclosed in a wooden shrine. (5) This image is a mask reproducing with remarkable fidelity both the features and complexion of the deceased. (6) On the occasion of public sacrifices they display these images, and decorate them with much care, and when any distinguished member of the family dies they take them to the funeral, putting them on men who seem to them to bear the closest resemblance to the original in stature and carriage. (7) These representatives wear togas, with a purple border if the deceased was a consul or praetor, whole purple if he was a censor, and embroidered with gold if he had celebrated a triumph or achieved anything similar” (translation by W.R. Paton, Loeb).

83. Before this period, just Titus Tatius, Numa Pompilius and Ancus Martius had been depicted on Roman Republican coin obverses: cp. *RRC* 344, 346/1 and 3f., 425 (with the remarks by SUSPÈNE 2008, p. 463f.).

84. Cic. *Phil.* 2.26: *Etenim, si auctores ad liberandam patriam desiderarentur illis actoribus, Brutos ego impellerem, quorum uterque L. Bruti imaginem cotidie videret, alter etiam Ahalae?*

85. Nep. *Att.* 18.3 ([...] *ut M. Bruti rogatu Iuniam familiam a stirpe ad hanc aetatem ordine enumeraverit* [sc. Atticus], *notans, qui a quoque ortus quos honores quibusque temporibus cepisset*) and Cic. *Att.* 13.40.1 (*ubi igitur φιλοτέχνημα illud tuum quod vidi in Parthenone* [apparently a part of one of the villas of M. Brutus], *Ahalam et Brutum?*). For family trees in *atria* in general, see Plin. *n. h.* 35.6 (with FLOWER 1996, p. 40, n. 51).

86. Thus LAHUSEN 1989, p. 39.

87. FLOWER 1996, p. 5-6. The ancestor portraits held by the so-called “togatus Barberini” are often interpreted as wax *imagines* (see, e.g., DRERUP 1980, p. 105 and LAHUSEN 2010, p. 213), but recent scholarship has convincingly shown that this is not the case. See LANG 2009, p. 386 and especially the illuminating article on the statue by Petra Cain, in FITTSCHEN, ZANKER, CAIN 2010, p. 48-51, esp. 49f.: the bust in the left hand of the *togatus* originally depicted a woman and was later reworked into the portrait of a man.

88. FLOWER 1996, p. 37.

the actors at funerals to breathe and also to speak.⁸⁹ In this author's opinion, one may certainly conjecture that the masks covered just the face/head, and perhaps also part of the neck, but surely did not display any drapery. Otherwise Polybius, in what is the best account of a Roman Republican funeral, would not specifically mention the careful choice of the appropriate types of toga by the men parading the ancestors' masks.⁹⁰

It is utterly out of the question to suppose that the ancestor portraits on Republican coins were directly copied from the *imagines* in the moneyers' cupboards, to be sure: these are numismatic portraits, of course, not depictions of masks,⁹¹ and they are designed according to the conventions of the art form as developed and expressed in Hellenistic or earlier Roman coin portraits.⁹² As for the models of the numismatic ancestor images, caution is in place, too. Some passages in Pliny's *naturalis historia* (35.7 and 12f.) as well as modern research make it clear that the *imagines* of wax were by no means the only class of ancestral effigies in and around the homes of the nobility: there were (probably three-dimensional) *aliae imagines* of the most important family members around the entrance, shield portraits (*imagines clipeatae*) in the house, etc.⁹³ Still, the *cerae* were doubtless the most distinctive class of images available, and they were unquestionably the most traditional form of Roman portraiture.

Hence, it seems plausible to infer that the *imagines* of wax exercised at least some influence on the design of the impressive Republican portraits of ancestors, both in sculpture and on coins. The numismatic portraits and the *imagines* (especially when paraded in funerals) were similar in purpose, after all: they were intended to celebrate the virtues of past generations, to encourage emulation and to enhance the status of the family concerned.⁹⁴ Up to now, scholarship has, in general, preferred to remain rather vague over the relationship between the coin portraits and the *cerae*, although a potential connection has been taken into consideration and some statements doubtless point in the right direction.⁹⁵ The decisive link between the portraits in both media seems to be that the focus was on the rendering of the facial features of the men. The hyper-realistic depictions of the ancestors' faces on the coins of the fifties and forties BC are among the most important testimonies of the naturalistic style of Republican portraiture.

89. Compare Suet. *Vesp.* 19.2.

90. Pol. 6.53.7: see n. 82 above.

91. For numismatic depictions of masks (without a neck), see *RRC* 337/1, 341/6f., 342/1f. and 449/1.

92. On this point, see ZEHACKER 1973, vol. 2, p. 972.

93. FLOWER 1996, p. 40-46.

94. On the social function of the *imagines*, see esp. LAHUSEN 1985, p. 268-274.

95. See, for example, FLOWER 1996, p. 86 ("It seems [...] relevant to consider the role of the *imagines* in everyday life as an inspiration for images on coins.") or LAHUSEN 2010, p. 214 ("Auch in dieser Bildnisgattung [sc. on coins] wurden die für die *imagines maiorum* so typischen Bildformeln eingesetzt.")

And lifelike representation was also the essence of wax *imagines*, to judge from the literary evidence: *vividus* is among the adjectives used to describe them.⁹⁶ In a formal respect, the fact that male ancestor portraits on coins of the Later Roman Republic are never represented with drapery, but are always shown just as heads, might be explained by some influence of the undraped *imagines maiorum* on coin design. The numismatic portraits of Julius Caesar and the first four Julio-Claudian emperors derive directly from the Republican coin portraits of ancestors, and this is why they are always undraped, too. Female coin portraits, on the contrary, developed a different tradition in that they always exhibit drapery: there were no female *imagines*.

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96. Mart. 7.44.2: *cuius adhuc vultum vivida cera tenet*.

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Figure 1 - Rome, Tessera. BUTTREY 1973, p. 62, no. 17. Classical Numismatic Group, Lancaster PA, 57, 4 April 2001, lot 1048. Ex J. Schulman, Amsterdam, 17 June 1924, lot 4.

Figure 2 - Ptolemy III, AV-Octodrachm.
SNG Copenhagen 196. Sincona AG, Zürich, 10, 27 May 2013, lot 204.

Figure 3 - Ptolemy V, AV-Octodrachm. MACDONALD 1905, Ptolemy V, no. 12 (plate 83, no. 11). Numismatica Ars Classica, Zürich-London, 52, 7 October 2009, lot 198.

Figure 4 - Trajan, Sestertius. WOYTEK 2010, 338u.
National Archaeological Museum, Firenze.

Figure 5 - Rome, Semuncia. *RRC* 39/5.
Auktionshaus H. D. Rauch, Wien, 87, 8 December 2010, lot 199.

Figure 6 - Rome, Denarius. *RRC* 234/1.
Classical Numismatic Group, Lancaster PA, Triton 12, 6 January 2009, lot 467.

Figure 7 - Rome, Denarius. *RRC* 292/1.
ArtCoins Roma, Roma, 6, 10 December 2012, lot 555.

Figure 8 - Rome, Denarius. *RRC* 297/1b (K, dot above).
Numismatik Lanz, München, 155, 10 December 2012, lot 379.

Figure 9 - Rome, Denarius. *RRC* 298/1.
Gorny & Mosch, Giessener Münzhandlung, München, 196, 7 March 2011, lot 2393.

Figure 10 - Rome, Denarius. *RRC* 329/1d (E).
Fritz Rudolf Künker, Osnabrück, 133, 11 October 2007, lot 8339.

Figure 11 - Rome, Denarius. *RRC* 354/1.

Classical Numismatic Group, Lancaster PA, 79, 17 September 2008, lot 899.

Figure 12 - Rome, Denarius. *RRC* 345/1.

Roma Numismatics, London, 5, 23 March 2013, lot 543.

Figure 13 - Rome, Denarius. *RRC* 435/1.

Gorny & Mosch, Giessener Münzhandlung, München, 118, 14 October 2002, lot 1896.

Figure 14 - Rome, Denarius. *RRC* 399/1a (fish, D).

Numismatica Ars Classica, Zürich-London, 63, 17 May 2012, lot 216.

Figure 15 - Eukratides I, Tetradrachm. *BOPEARACHCHI* 1991, Eucratide I, série 8.

Numismatica Ars Classica, Zürich-London, 33, 6 April 2006, lot 179.

Figure 16 - Rome, Denarius. *RRC* 293/1.

Gorny & Mosch, Giessener Münzhandlung, München, 204, 5 March 2012, 1939.

Figure 17 - Rome, Denarius. *RRC* 448/2.

Staatliche Museen zu Berlin, Münzkabinett, acc. 1832 Arditi. Objektnummer 18202018.

(© <http://www.smb.museum/ikmk/>)

Figure 18 - Rome, Denarius. *RRC* 433/2.

Numismatica Ars Classica, Zürich-London, 63, 17 May 2012, lot 319.

Figure 19 - Rome, Denarius. *RRC* 434/1.

Gorny & Mosch, Giessener Münzhandlung, München, 151, 9 October 2006, lot 343.

Figure 20 - Rome, Denarius. *RRC* 455/1a.

Numismatica Ars Classica, Zürich-London, 63, 17 May 2012, lot 369.

Figure 21 - Rome, Denarius. *RRC* 480/2a.

Classical Numismatic Group, Lancaster PA, Triton 16, 8 January 2013, lot 895.

Figure 22 - Rome, Denarius. *RRC* 480/22.

Numismatica Ars Classica, Zürich-London, 63, 17 May 2012, lot 460.

Figure 23 - Caligula, Denarius. *RIC* I², Caligula 8.

Numismatica Ars Classica, Zürich-London, 62, 6 October 2011, lot 2020.

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24a (2:1)

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Figure 24 - Mark Antony, Denarius. *RRC* 527/1.

Staatliche Museen zu Berlin, Münzkabinett, acc. 1891/461 (from the Castagneto hoard).
Objektnummer 18202297 (© <http://www.smb.museum/ikmk/>).

Figure 24a - As 24, 200%.

Figure 25 - Cleopatra and Mark Antony, Denarius. *RRC* 543/1.

Classical Numismatic Group, Lancaster PA, Triton 7, 12 January 2004, lot 839.

Figure 26 - Cleopatra and Mark Antony, Tetradrachm. *RPC* 4094.

Numismatica Ars Classica, Zürich-London, 54, 24 March 2010, lot 284.

Figure 27 - Mark Antony, Cistophorus. *RPC* 2202.

Classical Numismatic Group, Lancaster PA, 81, 20 May 2009, lot 973.

Figure 28 - Claudius for Antonia, Dupondius. *RIC* I², Claudius, 104.

Numismatica Ars Classica, Zürich-London, 64, 17 May 2012, lot 1089.

Figure 29 - Claudius, Cistophorus. *RPC* 2224.

Ira and Larry Goldberg Coins, Los Angeles CA, 60, 21 September 2010, lot 2360.

Figure 30 - Ptolemy II, AV-Octodrachm.

SNG Copenhagen 132. Sincona AG, Zürich, 10, 27 May 2013, lot 197.